

Environmental Awareness among Higher Secondary School Students in Coimbatore District in the Current Scenario

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Abstract: Environment refers to the sum total of conditions which surround man of a given point in space and time. The natural environment is composed of atmosphere earth, water and space. If natural environment remain clean and it is quite enjoyable then, the unpolluted environment is called as a normal one and then interaction of the atmosphere, lithosphere, and hydrosphere with biosphere always continues to create a normal natural environment, unfortunately, on account of industrialization, population, explosion, construction, transportation. The composition and complex nature of the environment gets change. Environment in developing countries like India have been threatened by problems like poverty, pollution, over population and degradation and depletion of environment for this study environmental awareness should be provide to the school as its foundation helps the individual to be are responsible citizen.

Keywords: Environmental Awareness, Climate Change, Over Population, Pollutions and Sustainability.

Introduction

Environmental awareness shapes a hierarchy of values and at the same time has an influence on the sense of responsibility for inappropriate choice of values. The school students awareness of the environment means the ability to emotionally understand the surrounding world, including the laws of the natural environment, sensitivity to all the changes occurring in the environment, understanding of cause and effect relationships between the quality of the environment and human behaviour, an understanding of how the environment works as a system and a sense of responsibility for the common heritage of the earth, such as natural resources with the aim of preserving them for future generations. The knowledge acquired during school education and then systematically improved in adulthood, is an essential factor in heightening the environmental awareness of an individual and at the same time, an indispensable condition for the development of a pro-ecological life style.

Significance of the study

Normally the most obvious concerns about the environment is associated with many projects by means of any development are the various forms of pollution. In the wake of the awaking on environmental issues that swept across the world. This education was included in the curricula with the idea to sensitize the students. It is very essentials to safe guard and enhances the environment for the benefit to present and future generations. An environmental awareness in decision making process for all the activities and the research project has to be created. New initiatives and additional measures are required to complement existing efforts to achieve sustainable development with conservation of natural resources and sound management of the environment. Hanisch et.al (2014) explains the environmental awareness is very

important for environmental management as well as the protection of the living organism. Agarwal (2018) states that environmental awareness is performance in an integrated manner by all elements of the people. This study will help to know about the environmental awareness.

Statement of the problem

The investigator has selected the present study with the aim of knowing the level of environmental awareness among high school, and therefore, it has been entitled as "Environmental Awareness among Higher Secondary School Students in Coimbatore District".

Definitions of the terms

Environmental Awareness

Environmental awareness is defined as factual information possessed by a student about environmental issues, facts and events in the content area of ecosystem. It refers to the students studying in XII standards in higher secondary schools.

Research objectives

- ❖ To study the environmental awareness among the male and female higher secondary school students of Coimbatore district.
- ❖ To find out the environmental awareness among higher secondary school of students of interest in gardening of Coimbatore district.

Hypotheses of the study

- ❖ There is no significant mean score difference between male and female of higher school students in their environmental awareness.
- ❖ There is no significant mean score difference between interest in gardening areas of higher secondary school students in their environmental awareness.

Method of Study

The investigator used the survey method for collecting data through Google forms.

Population

The population for the study was higher secondary school students in Coimbatore district.

Tools Used

Environmental awareness questionnaire prepared and validated by investigator and the guide. The questionnaire consists of 45 items in the form of a statement. It has both positive and negative items, each a statement has two alternatives responses, namely yes and No. The investigator given the score “One” for “Yes” response to positive statements, otherwise “Zero” and the investigator given the score “ONE” for “NO” response to

negative statement, otherwise “ZERO”. The maximum score for this scale is 45 and the minimum is 0.

Statistical techniques used

- ❖ Mean
- ❖ Standard deviation and ‘t’ test were used to analyses the data

Testing Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant mean score difference between male and female of higher secondary school students in their environmental awareness.

Table -1

It showing the significant mean score difference between male and female of higher secondary school students in their environmental awareness.

Variable	Category	N	Mean	S.D.	‘t’-Value	Remarks (at 0.05 level)
Gender	Male	125	83.7	13.17	2.800	Significant
	Female	125	79.5	11.32		

The obtained value 2.800 is greater than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significant it is concluded that there is a significant difference between the male and female higher secondary school students with respect to their environmental awareness.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant mean score difference between interest in gardening higher secondary school students in their environmental awareness.

Table -1

It showing the significant mean score difference between urban and rural areas of higher secondary school students in their environmental awareness.

Variable	Description	N	Mean	S.D.	‘t’-Value	Remarks (at 0.05 level)
Interest in Gardening	Yes	178	30.67	9.26	0.765	Not Significant
	No	72	31.61	9.15		

The obtained value 0.765 is lower than the table value 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the interests in gardening wise higher secondary school students with respect to their environmental awareness.

Findings of the study

The following are the important findings of the study

1. There is a significant mean score difference between male and female of higher secondary school students in their environmental awareness.
2. There is no significant mean score difference between interest in gardening areas of higher secondary school students in their environmental awareness.

Recommendations

1. Environmental awareness enriches one’s knowledge of balance of nature.

2. A higher degree of environmental awareness is essential to save the world and preserve the eco system.
3. Research on environmental awareness associated with preservations of nature.
4. The schools may conduct seminars, debates and essay writing, drawing competitions on global warming.
5. Co-curricular and extracurricular activities should be encouraged to promote awareness on global warming.
6. Every college and school should take steps to develop knowledge in environmental awareness.
7. Everyone should take care in keeping their surroundings clean and hygiene.
8. Environmental awareness plays a significant role in the development of every individual life. Hence, the awareness about environmental should be given to the students at all level of education.

9. Parents and teachers should provide positive environment to develop environmental awareness of the children.
10. The students should be made to inculcate the habit of planning more trees and create a green revolution.

Conclusion

The students have a higher level of scientific attitude. The results and findings of the study provide important insight in the development of knowledge in the environmental awareness among secondary school students because they are future builder of the society. The continuous maintenance of quality environment for many years is called sustainable development. The environment and its resources must not be allowed to degrade. The natural resources must be used in limited way. It produced an ideal balanced ecosystem, all the components for available for the future generations. Through this research, it is known that, environmental awareness is seen among students. But every student is not taking any steps to product and conserves the environment.

Reference

1. Lenka, S.K (2005). Awareness of Environmental Education among the PG Students. *Edutracks*, 35-38 August.
2. Mrunalini @ Sankariah (2010), Attitude and Reflections of Perspective Teachers on Environmental Concerns. *Journal of Educational Research* Vol. 1 (2), 24-31.
3. Mercy, A., and Arjunan, N.K (2005). Environmental Attitude and Pro-Environmental

- Bahaviour among Secondary School Children. *Edu tracks*, 32-34.
4. Prashant kumar Astalin (2013), Environmental Awareness in senior secondary students of CBSE and U.P. Board in Kanpur Mahanagar. *Research and Reflection on Education* Vol.11(3), 13-15.
5. Stevenson, R.B “Schooling and Environmental Education: Contradictions in purpose and Pracatice” / *Environmental Education Research* / Vol.13, no.2, 2007, PP. 139-53.
6. Sharma. V.S (2006). “Environmental Education” /Anmol publications pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, the world book of Encyclopedia, Volume 6 pages No.330-332.
7. Sarojini.K. “Level of Environmental Awareness Among School Students”, *Edutracks* Vol.9(1) july, 2010, PP.10-12.
8. Suyatna and Rosidin (2016). Assessment model for critical Thinking in Learning Global Warming Scientific Approach. *Proceedings of International Conference on Educational Research and Evaluation*, 1-7. Yogyakarta; Yogyakarta State University.
9. M1 Evelyn @ TI Tyav (2012), Environmental Pollution in Nilgeria. The need for Awareness creation for sustainable development, *Jouranal of research in forestry, wildlife and environment*, Vol.4(2).
10. Syed Aftab Iqbal.(2011). *Pollution the ugly face of Environment* New Delhi Discovery Publishing house Pvt. Ltd.